

Effect of B substitution on structural and magnetic properties of Zr-Co melt spun ribbons

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Abstract

Rare earth free permanent magnets have drawn much attention recently due to limited mineral resources and scarce supply of rare earth metals [1-3]. Among the rare earth free compounds, Zr_2Co_{11} is a prospective candidate that displays high uniaxial anisotropy (1.1 MJ/m^3) and Curie temperature ($500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) [4, 5]. The present work focuses on investigation of effect of substitution of B in Zr-Co on structural and magnetic properties. As the phase required is stable at high temperature rapid solidification has been employed to prepare the ribbons of $Zr_{16}Co_{84-x}B_x$ ($x = 0, 1, 2, \text{ and } 3$) and the investigated the properties in both as-spun and heat-treated conditions. The x-ray diffraction (XRD) and thermo magnetic analysis revealed that substitution of B reduces the amount of soft-magnetic Co phase and increases the amount of hard-magnetic Co_2Zr_{11} phase. The addition of B in the Co–Zr melt-spun ribbons resulted in the improvement of magnetic properties, especially the coercivity. In the as-spun ribbons, with increase of B from $x=0$ to $x=3$ the coercivity increases from 0.8 to 2 KOe, while the magnetization decreases from 69 to 58 emu/g. The optimum magnetic properties of coercivity of 2.4 KOe and saturation magnetization of 77 emu/g was obtained for $x=2$ ribbon heat-treated at 550°C for 30 min.

Key words: rare earth free magnet, $Co_{11}Zr_2$, magnetic properties

References:

- [1] J.M.D. Coey, IEEE Trans. Magn. Vol. 47, pp. 4671- 4681, 2011.
- [2] M.J. Kramer, R.W. [McCallum](#), I.A. [Anderson](#), S. [Constantinides](#), JOM J. Minerals, Metals and Mater. Soc. vol.64, pp. 752-763, 2012.

- [3] [3] N.V. Rama Rao, A.M. Gabay, G.C. Hadjipanayis, J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys. Vol. 46, pp. 062001-1-062001-4, 2013